

Flemi chapparin—A New Chalcone from *Flemingia chappar*

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In an earlier communication¹ we reported from *Flemingia chappar* (Fam. Leguminosae) the first natural occurrence of a simple, biogenetically important chalcone (2', 4'-dihydroxy-chalcone). Further investigation has resulted in the isolation of another new chalcone designated as Flemi chapparin from the same source. Structure-elucidation of this new chalcone is reported in this communication.

Flemi chapparin, m.p. 158–60°, crystallises from benzene as bright orange prisms and analyses for C₁₆H₁₄O₄ (M⁺ 270). The colour reactions (negative shinoda and a greenish brown ferric colour) and the UV [λ_{max}^{MeOH} 225 (log ϵ 4.07), 313 m μ (log ϵ 4.32); λ_{min}^{MeOH} 252 (log ϵ 3.65), 355 m μ (log ϵ 3.99); no appreciable change in the maxima with N/10 alkali] absorptions indicated it to be a chalcone. It contains a phenolic-OH (ν_{max}^{Nujol} 3200 cm⁻¹, 6.45 δ), conjugated >C=O (ν_{max}^{KBr} 1640 cm⁻¹) and a—OCH₃ (3H singlet at 3.95 δ) group.

The N.M.R. spectrum (60 Mc/sec in CDCl₃) of Flemi chapparin also discloses the presence of α and β protons of the chalcone² at 7.35 (doublet, $J = 16$ c/s) and 7.9 δ (doublet, $J = 16$ c/s) respectively. Two sharp singlets at 6.66 and 7.28 δ and five aromatic protons around 7.3–7.8 δ are also discernible in the spectrum.

The mass spectral data of Flemi chapparin exhibit, in addition to the molecular ion peak at m/e 270, two prominent peaks at m/e 193 (M–77, M–C₆H₅⁺) and at m/e 166 (M–106, M–C₆H₅CH=CH₂) proving the unsubstituted nature of the B ring of this chalcone³. A medium intensity peak at m/e 151 (m/e 166–15), arising by loss of methyl from the –OCH₃ group, is also recorded in the spectrum.

Flemi chapparin on treatment with aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.5%) and subsequent acidification gives a flavanone, C₁₆H₁₄O₄, crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) as colourless needles, m.p. 180–81° (a deep red colour in the shinoda and a negative ferric reactions). It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium carbonate. The IR spectrum (Nujol) shows a weak carbonyl band (1642 cm⁻¹) and no –OH absorption. The UV spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 240 (log ϵ 3.40), 280 (log ϵ 3.55) and 346 m μ (log ϵ 3.38); $\lambda_{\frac{1}{2}0max}^{NEthanolic-NaOH}$ 260, 280 and 350 m μ] resembles closely those of 6, 7, 3', 4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone derivatives⁴.

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3. H. Audier, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1962, 2893.
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Similarity in properties of the above flavanone with 7-hydroxyflavanone (negative ferric chloride reaction, solubility in sodium carbonate, similarity in IR spectra, bathochromic shift of UV, etc.) suggests the presence of a phenolic-OH group in the 7-position of this flavanone.

The N.M.R. spectrum (60 Mc/sec in CDCl_3) of the flavanone, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$, signals at 7.49 (singlet, 5H aromatic), 7.4 and 6.62 (two singlets, aromatic), 6.42 (singlet, disappears on D_2O exchange, phenolic -OH), 5.46 (1H quartet, $J = 5$ c/s, C-2H), 3.95 (singlet, $-\text{OCH}_3$) and 2.9 δ (2H triplet, $J = 5$ c/s, C-3H).

The N.M.R. data suggest the substitution pattern I rather than II and III for the flavanone on the basis of the following facts. In phloroglucinol type (II) of flavanone, the C-6 and C-8 protons appear, as a general rule, at 5.8 and 6.1 δ respectively. The absence of a low field aromatic proton above 7.68 δ without any *ortho* coupling rules out the possibility of a substitution pattern of type III. In structure I the two aromatic singlets at 6.62 and 7.4 δ can be reasonably assigned to C-8 and C-5 protons respectively.**

On the basis of the data presented above, two alternative structures Ia and Ib may be assigned to the flavanone from Flemi chapparin. Of these, Ia is considered to be the plausible structure for the flavanone since a direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., i.r.) of the latter with authentic 7-methoxy-6-hydroxy flavanone (Ib) proved to be different. Accordingly, the structure of Flemi chapparin may be represented as IV. Synthetic evidences are being sought to clarify the proposed structure of Flemi chapparin.

**** Note added in proof :**

Besides, methylation of the flavanone $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ with diazomethane affords the corresponding dimethylether, m.p. 170–71°. The physical properties (m.p., i.r., u.v. and green colour in the Shinoda reaction) agree with those reported for 6, 7-dimethoxyflavanone (G. Bargellini and G. B. Marini-Bettolo, *Gazz. Chem. Ital.*, 1940, **70**, 170) thereby confirming the substitution pattern I for the flavanone.

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